

Study of Medial Meniscus Tear Pattern and Cartilage Loss in Patients Undergoing TKR with Severe Osteoarthritis Knee with Varus DeformitySai Kumar Reddy Mukkamalla¹, D. Pavan Kumar², B. Kiran³¹Assistant Professor, Department of Orthopaedics, Viswabharathi Medical College and Hospital, Kurnool, Andhra Pradesh, India^{2,3}Junior Resident, Department of Orthopaedics, Viswabharathi Medical College and Hospital, Kurnool, Andhra Pradesh

Received: 25-04-2024 / Revised: 23-05-2024 / Accepted: 26-06-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Introduction:** The meniscus is a vital structure to normal knee function responsible for body weight distribution, shock absorption, proprioception, stabilization, lubrication of the knee joint, and pressure resistance. A variety of recent research has focused on the loss of circumferential hoop tension as the main precursor of onset and progression of osteoarthritis.**Aim:** To investigate the incidence of root tears of the posterior horn of the medial meniscus and cartilage loss in total knee replacement arthroplasty for knee osteoarthritis and retrospectively analyze clinical results and factors associated with root tears and cartilage loss.**Materials and Methods:** There were 101 knees of 74 enrolled patients who had undergone total knee replacement arthroplasty between January 2023 and December 2023 in Viswabharathi Medical College and Hospital, Kurnool. The presence of a root tear of the posterior horn of the medial meniscus was confirmed in all patients. Statistical analysis was performed to investigate the correlation between root tears and the possible factors of meniscal tears including gender, age, body mass index (BMI), varus deformity and activity of the patient.**Results:** Meniscal tears were observed in 101 patients with complete root degeneration in 55 patients (P value <0.05), thin roots in 9 patients and with intact root in 37 patients. The Patients with complete root tear showed tricompartmental cartilage loss compared to other 2 groups.**Conclusions:** Factors considered to represent the severity of osteoarthritis were found to be associated with root tears of the medial meniscus posterior horn and cartilage loss. Female sex, sedentary activity, Increased BMI seemed to be associated with the increased incidence of root tears of the medial meniscus posterior horn.**Keywords:** Osteoarthritis Knee, Medial Meniscus, Root of Medial Meniscus, Cartilage loss, Total Knee Replacement, Varus Deformity.

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Introduction

The meniscus is a vital structure to normal knee function responsible for body weight distribution, shock absorption, proprioception, stabilization and lubrication of the knee joint, and pressure resistance [1-5]. In particular, the weight-bearing function of the meniscus by circumferential hoop tension is directly associated with prevention of osteoarthritis of the knee. In order to maintain the circumferential hoop tension, the attachment of the anterior and posterior horns of the meniscus to the tibia should be secured and the meniscus collagen fiber orientation should be maintained [7]. However, a radial tear or root tear of the meniscus may lead to loss of circumferential hoop tension, which eventually results in osteoarthritis of the knee [8]. In this study, we assessed

intraoperatively tear pattern of the posterior root of the medial meniscus and cartilage loss mapping in patients who underwent total knee arthroplasty (TKA) for osteoarthritis and evaluated the relationship between clinical parameters and the root tears.

Materials and Methods:

After Obtaining Institutional Ethical Committee approval we started patient enrollment to our study from January 2023 to December 2023. We got 74 patients with 101 knees in Viswabharathi Medical College and Hospital, Kurnool. Out of 101 Knees, 76 Knees were female and 25 were Male. Our Inclusion criteria includes Patients willing for surgery, All Knees with Grade IV Degenerative Oste-

oarthritis with Varus deformity, Exclusion Criteria Patients with Valgus knee deformity, Rheumatoid arthritis, Malignancy, Infective etiology, Post traumatic knees and unfit for Surgery. Pre-Operative activity levels have been assessed with the help of Knee Injury and Osteoarthritis Outcome score (KOOS score). Tear pattern of the root has been classified Root intact, complete degeneration of root, thin root. We observed the tear pattern of root of Medial Meniscus and Cartilage loss intra operatively and did analyzed their correlation with possible factors of meniscal tears including gender, age, body mass index (BMI), varus deformity and activity of the patient. Cartilage loss has been graded according to ICRS classification.

Results:

Meniscal tears were observed in 101 patients with complete root degeneration in 55 patients (P value <0.05), thin roots in 9 patients and with intact root in 37 patients.

The Patients with complete root tear showed tricompartmental cartilage loss compared to other 2 groups.

We classified the observed root tear pattern in Kellgren Lawrence Grade IV Osteoarthritis patients with three categories: Thin root, Root Intact and No root (complete degeneration of root) and graded the cartilage loss according to ICRS grading Classification. Out of 101 Knees, we found 55 knees complete root degeneration, 9 thin root and in 37 knees there is intact root. Average cartilage loss in Femur side is 8.25 quadrants and Tibia side 6.75 quadrants.

Figure 1: Intact Root

Figure 2: Complete Degenerated Root

Figure 3: Very Thin Root

Table 1: Statistical Analysis:

Gender & Age Group (yrs)	No Root	Root present	Thin Root	Grand Total
Female	51%	38%	11%	100%
45-55	71%	6%	23%	100%
55-66	33%	61%	6%	100%
65-76	65%	26%	9%	100%
Male	64%	32%	4%	100%
55-65	75%	17%	8%	100%
65-76	54%	46%	0%	100%
Grand Total	54%	37%	9%	100%

In Females the root degeneration is 51%. And the age group involved the complete root degeneration is 45-55yrs old. In males the complete root degeneration is seen in 64% while the age group is 55-65yrs. Over all, we found 63% medial meniscus root tear pattern in Osteoarthritis knee patients in which complete root degeneration seen in 54% and 9% with very thin root have been observed.

Table 2: BMI:

Gender	No Root	Root Present	Thin Root	Grand Total
Female	51%	38%	11%	100%
Normal	86%	14%	0%	100%
Obese	50%	39%	11%	100%
Over weight	45%	42%	13%	100%
Male	64%	32%	4%	100%
Normal	100%	0%	0%	100%
Obese	45%	45%	10%	100%
Over Weight	77%	23%	0%	100%
Grand Total	54%	37%	9%	100%

In Normal Females (18-24) of BMI the complete degeneration of tear is 86%. In Males 77% with Overweight has complete degeneration of root tear.

Table 3: Activity:

Gender & Activity	No Root	Root Present	Thin Root	Grand Total
Female	51%	38%	11%	100%
Heavy Worker	0%	0%	100%	100%
Sedentary	53%	39%	8%	100%
Male	64%	32%	4%	100%
Heavy Worker	75%	25%	0%	100%
Sedentary	59%	35%	6%	100%
Grand Total	54%	37%	9%	100%

In Females sedentary activity and Heavy worker males has complete degeneration of root.

Table 4:

Average of HKA	No Root	Root Present	Thin Root	Grand Total
Female	167.18	168.01	166.40	167.42
45-55	171.76	174.90	168.23	171.11
55-65	164.78	166.98	162.15	165.98
65-76	165.44	170.65	167.00	166.93
Male	166.63	169.46	170.20	168.52
55-65	168.41	168.15	170.20	168.52
65-76	164.33	169.90		166.90
Grand Total	167.02	168.33	166.82	167.48

As the age progresses the Varus Deformity progression occurs. The deformity is more the complete root tear is observed in both males and females.

Table 5:

Average of MPTA	No Root	Root Present	Thin Root	Grand Total
Female	83.43	84.87	84.46	84.09
45-55	85.14	81.10	86.13	85.14
55-65	83.26	83.76	79.45	83.36
65-76	82.19	89.55	86.15	84.46
Male	84.14	85.18	83.10	84.43
55-65	84.71	84.70	83.10	84.58
65-76	83.40	85.33		84.29
Grand Total	83.63	84.94	84.31	84.17

As the MPTA decreases the degeneration of root also increased. We did Chi square test to find the correlation between the factors influencing the tear and cartilage loss pattern. We found out that there is relationship between age group and root pattern. May be our sample size is small to conclude on activity of the patient and varus deformity of the patient. Cartilage loss is seen more in Femur side compared to Tibia. In Femur average of 8.25 quadrants loss of cartilage present compared to tibia 6.75 quadrants. Therefore the cartilage loss on femoral side is noticed compared to tibial side.

Discussion:

The meniscus plays an important role in body weight distribution, shock absorption, proprioception, and stabilization and lubrication of the knee joint [1-5], all of which could become impossible if the meniscus is torn or displaced. A complete radial tear or complex tear at the posterior horn insertion site of the meniscus causes displacement of the meniscus, which may

eventually lead to development of osteoarthritis [12,13]. In other words, mechanical alterations in the knee joint due to increased load on a particular compartment in the knee result in chondral and subchondral damage.

Osteoarthritis of the knee was first described in 1968 by Ahlback et al. [14] who had conducted research on senior female patients. So far, the causes of knee osteoarthritis have been investigated in a variety of studies, and meniscal pathology has been particularly associated with the degenerative condition of the knee [15-18]. Ahlback et al. [14] noted meniscal tears in 6 out of 14 osteoarthritis patients (42.9%). Norman and Baker [19] observed meniscal tears in 50%–78% of their patients.

Since Pagnani et al. [20] documented arthroscopic evidence of accelerated degeneration of the articular cartilage in a 20-year-old football player with a posterior root tear of the medial meniscus in 1991; attention has been brought to meniscal tears as the main precursor of the development of

osteoarthritis. Robertson et al. [21] noted tears of the posterior root of the medial meniscus in 80% of their patients with osteoarthritis. Bin et al. [9] reported radial tears of the posterior horn accounted for 27.8% of the medial meniscal tears. Bessette [2] emphasized the importance of maintaining hoop tension to preserve the normal meniscus function, which decreases more drastically in cases of radial tears of the anterior or posterior horn than the mid body of the meniscus. Ozkoc et al. [22] reported that posterior horn root tears are more frequent in the medial than lateral meniscus due to the greater mobility of the posterior horn attachment to the tibia in the lateral meniscus. Allaire et al. [12] described that the influence of posterior root tears of the medial meniscus on knee biomechanics was equivalent to that of meniscectomy in a cadaver model. They attributed loss of hoop tension of the meniscus resulting in the inability to distribute body weight and subluxation of the meniscus to greater contact pressure in the knee joint and early development of articular cartilage degeneration.

In the current study, based on a review of the above mentioned studies presenting posterior root tears of the medial meniscus as the main causative factor of osteoarthritis, we attempted to investigate the relationship between the meniscal tears and clinical factors. Meniscal tears were observed in 101 patients with complete root degeneration in 55 patients (P value <0.05), thin roots in 9 patients and with intact root in 37 patients. The Patients with complete root tear showed tricompartmental cartilage loss compared to other 2 groups. LaPrade first classified Meniscus root tears [23].

We classified the observed root tear pattern in Kellgren Lawrence Grade IV Osteoarthritis patients with three categories: Thin root, Root Intact and No root (complete degeneration of root) and graded the cartilage loss according to ICRS grading Classification. Out of 101 Knees, we found 55 knees complete root degeneration, 9 thin root and in 37 knees there is intact root.

Average cartilage loss in Femur side is 8.25 quadrants and Tibia side 6.75 quadrants. However, considering that most of the patients were advanced age, the tears could have resulted from degenerative changes in the joint because BMI is correlated with the load on the medial compartment of the knee in advanced stage osteoarthritis. Factors potentially related to the severity of osteoarthritis, such as Kellgren-Lawrence grading scale, varus deformity, and medial deviation of the mechanical axis, showed significant relationship with posterior root tears of the medial meniscus.

There were some limitations of this study. First, although the presence of a root tear was determined, it was difficult to avoid the influence of subjective judgement, and the causal relation

between osteoarthritis and meniscal tears should be further verified. Second, the study was based only on the influence of Posterior horn of medial meniscus and medial meniscal tears on the progression of osteoarthritis; possible impact of accompanying meniscal tears was not considered as a variable in the analysis. Third, our sample size is small to conclude some factors influence on the Posterior horn of medial meniscus and its progression to Osteoarthritis Knee.

Conclusion:

Age is associated with root tear pattern while BMI and Sex are not associated with root tear pattern and cartilage loss. Therefore to comment on severity of varus deformity and activity associated with root tear pattern and cartilage loss our sample size is too small.

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